

Twin on a chip brains for monitoring individual sleep habits

Document Title	Ethics Guidelines
Document Reference	D1.1
Authors	Chiara Magliaro, Arti Ahluwalia, Sonia Cerchio, Jens Schwamborn, Ugo Faraguna, Andrea Vecchi, Umberto Olcese
Version	
Report availability	PUBLIC
Date	December, 2 nd , 2024

This deliverable identifies the main ethical standards through which all the activities, experiments and initiatives linked to the NAP project must comply with. The deliverable indicates the ethical standards that will be implemented. It intends to detail the code of conduct of the *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments foreseen in NAP, as well as provide the project partners with necessary information required the ethics management of the project. Indeed, the deliverable addresses ethical, legal and security/privacy issues that may arise during the project's lifespan, identifying the requirements that need to be taken into consideration to let NAP to be and remain fully compliant. It also includes general guidelines, thus constituting an internal policy document on aspects to be taken into account by all the partners throughout the lifetime of the project.

It should be noticed that this report is delivered at an early stage of the project, since the aim is to present the main risks associated with the project itself and suggest some basic measures that should be undertaken by the project's partners to warrant compliance in the ethics and legal fields.

The document recalls the obligations related to ethics and research integrity set in the Grant Agreement and additional ethics principles, such as data management and privacy, gender balance, and informed consent when human beings are involved, that are of paramount importance in research. For each principle, the approach that will be adopted and the actions that will be performed by the partners to abide are indicated. Furthermore, a process for identifying and managing ethics-related issues is proposed. The process is based on a distributed responsibility where actors, working on the project at different levels, will be informed about the issues and will be responsible for highlighting the emergence of issues, discussing them with the proper coordinator (e.g. WP leaders), who will suggest the actions to be undertaken. In case issues cannot be managed at the level they are identified, an escalation process foresees the involvement of the Project Scientific Coordinator, the two Boards dealing with Ethical issues, and the General Assembly.

The deliverable is divided in different chapters, starting with a brief introduction to the ethical principles on issues related to health research conducted in EU. Then, we will detail the key ethics principles that guide the execution of the project, the process for monitoring and managing ethical issues, as well as the organisational structure and the tools that will be used.

History of changes:

Version	Data	Organization	Description/comments
1.0	August 5 th , 2023	UNIFI	First draft version
1.1	August 29 th , 2023	OT, SleepActa, UVA	Revised draft by the Beneficiaries
2.0	May 27 th , 2024	UNIFI, OT, SleepActa, UVA	Revised draft by all the Beneficiaries, taking into account the suggestions from the reviewers during the first review meeting.
2.1	December 2 th , 2024	UNIFI, OT, SleepActa, UVA	Revised draft by all the Beneficiaries, taking into account the suggestions from the reviewers, detailed within their report.

Table of Contents

<u>GENERAL PRINCIPLES FOR HEALTH RESEARCH IN EU</u>	<u>5</u>
<u>LOCATING ETHICS IN THE NAP PROJECT</u>	<u>8</u>
<u>ETHICS MANAGEMENT IN NAP</u>	<u>10</u>
ORGANIZATIONAL BODIES AND ETHICS MANAGEMENT	10
PRACTICES FOR MONITORING ETHICS MANAGEMENT	10
<u>CONCLUSIONS</u>	<u>12</u>
<u>APPENDIX</u>	<u>13</u>
APPENDIX 1 - ETHICAL DIMENSION OF THE OBJECTIVES, METHODOLOGY AND LIKELY IMPACT.....	13
USE OF STEM CELLS	13
ANIMAL EXPERIMENTS	13
HUMANS.....	14
APPENDIX 2 – ETHICS ISSUE TABLE OF THE NAP PROJECT	15

General principles for health research in EU

All EU-funded projects should be aligned with ethical principles and compliance. Indeed, as established by the HORIZON scheme, and especially article 19 of the Regulation 2021/695,

Actions carried out under the program shall comply with ethical principles and relevant Union, national and international legislation, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention of Human Rights and its supplementary protocols.

This is further remarked in the article 14 of the Model Grant Agreement, ‘Ethics and values’:

The action must be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national laws on ethical principles. The beneficiary must commit to and ensure the respect of basis EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities).

which also highlights the respect of the fundamental principles of research integrity set out in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity of ALLEA (ALL European Academies).

In general, ethics issues arise whenever research involves i) human participants and/or their cells/tissues, ii) personal data, iii) animals and iv) methods, materials or experiments that could harm the environment, research staff or participants; or when research is conducted i) in locations where the safety and security of researchers and participants may be jeopardized and ii) outside the EU, especially in countries lacking adequate regulation and/or have a limited capacity to enforce the relevant ethical standards and guidelines. Ethics issues can also take the form of concerns about the potential use or misuse of new technologies, innovations, applications or research findings – even where research projects have benign intentions.

In this scenario, it is clear why EU principles become even more specific when the performed research is related to health, as also shown by the ethics issues checklist that needs to be submitted along with the proposal and integrated in the Grant Agreement, after the screening performed by an independent ethics panel (Table 1).

Table 1 Ethics Issue Table

Human Embryonic Stem Cells and Human Embryos	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells?			
Does this activity involve Human Embryos?			
Humans	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve Human Participants?			
Are they volunteers for non-medical studies (e.g., social or human sciences research)?			
Are they healthy volunteers for medical studies?			
Are they patients for medical studies?			
Are they potentially vulnerable individuals or groups?			
Are they children/minors?			
Are they other persons unable to give informed consent?			
Does this activity involve interventions (physical also including imaging technology, behavioural treatments etc. on the study participants)?			

Does this activity involve conducting a clinical study as defined by the Clinical Trial Regulation (EU 536/2014)? (using pharmaceuticals, biologicals, radiopharmaceuticals, or advanced therapy medicinal products)			
Human cells/Tissues (not covered by Section1)	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve the use of human cells or tissues?			
Are they human embryonic or foetal cells or tissues?			
Are they available commercially?			
Are they obtained from this project?			
Are they obtained from another project, laboratory or institution?			
Are they obtained from biobanks?			
Personal Data	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve processing of personal data?			
Does this activity involve further processing of previously collected personal data (including use of preexisting data sets or sources, merging existing data sets)??			
It is planned to export personal data from the EU to non-EU countries? Specify the type of personal data and countries involved			
It is planned to export personal data from non-EU countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country? Specify the type of personal data and countries involved			
Does this activity involve the processing of personal data related to criminal convictions or offences?			
Animals	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve animals?			
Are they vertebrates?			
Are they non-human primates?			
Are they genetically-modified?			
Are they cloned farm animals?			
Are they endangered species?			
Non-EU countries	Yes	No	Page
Will some of the activities be carried out in non-EU countries?			
In case non-EU countries are involved, do the activities undertaken in these countries raise potential ethics issues?			
It is planned to use local resources (e.g. animal and/or human tissue samples, genetic material, live animals, human remains, materials of historical value, endangered fauna or flora samples, etc.)?			
Is it planned to import any material (other than data) from non-EU countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country?			
Is it planned to export any material (other than data) from the EU to non-EU countries?			
Does this activity involve low and/or lower middle-income countries, (if yes, detail the benefit -sharing actions planned in the self-assessment)			
Could the situation in the country put the individuals taking part in the activity at risk?			
Environment, Health and Safety	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve the use of substances or processes that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants (during the implementation of the activity or further to the			

use of the results, as a possible impact)?			
Does this activity deal with endangered fauna and/or flora / protected areas?			
Does this activity involve the use of substances or processes that may cause harm to humans, including those performing the activity (during the implementation of the activity or further to the use of the results, as a possible impact)			
Artificial Intelligence	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve the development, deployment and/or use of Artificial Intelligence? (if yes, detail in the self-assessment whether that could raise ethical concerns related to human rights and values and detail how this will be addressed).			
Other Ethics Issues	Yes	No	Page
Are there other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration?			

Locating ethics in the NAP project

Ethical issues are of crucial importance for research, innovation, science and technology. In NAP, key ethics principles have been already foreseen in the Grant Agreement. Particular attention will be paid to specific principles such as data management and privacy (further detailed in the Data Management Plan (D1.2)) and gender balance.

NAP raises ethical issues due to the involvement of human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSC), animal models and the use of human actigraphic data. These issues have been already identified by the consortium during the proposal stage. They are reported in the Grant Agreement and also in this deliverable. Their compliance with the EU regulation is described here.

Human Cells from healthy individuals and PD patients will be used in NAP. These particular hiPSCs have been already obtained at the involved research institutes/hospitals from biopsies according to the existing national and European legislations (e.g., Helsinki Declaration, article 19 of Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013, Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights of UNESCO of 11 November 1997). It is worth highlighting that a detailed list of all the hospitals/partners from where OT received cells cannot be provided, since they are under agreements with confidentiality clauses. The patient specific cell lines that OT is working with are pseudo-anonymized. Patient samples were collected after the patient or her/his parents/legal representatives provided informed written consent. Similarly, healthy, age-matched volunteers were recruited as controls after informed written consent, in accordance with applicable EU and National laws (in particular EU Directive 2004/23/EC). Indeed, the information sheet for the patients was authorized and approved by the National Research Ethics Committee of Luxembourg (decision 201305/04). It is expected that novel patient-derived cell lines will be acquired during this project. All donor related information is pseudo-anonymised, thereby the high level of data protection is guaranteed. The individual hiPSCs will be identified by a specific code number. They will be registered at Human Pluripotent Stem Cell Registry (<https://hpscereg.eu/>). The appropriate facilities for the handling of human cells are available. Even though it is the goal of the work of OT that knowledge, tools, and methods will be the basis for commercialisation efforts, neither the donor derived cells nor any derivatives from these cells will be involved in the filing of patents or the establishment of any other intellectual property rights. To be more explicit, e.g. protocols and procedures that have been developed using the donated cells will be patent protected, but not the cells and derivatives thereof themselves. Further, small molecules or other therapeutics developed with the cellular models will be patent protected, but not the cells and derivatives thereof themselves.

These biological samples will be shipped from OT to the partners in Pisa (UNIFI) and Amsterdam (UVA) for further structural, metabolic and functional analyses. These include e.g. metabolic modelling, imaging and recordings of neuronal activity via Calcium imaging. The hiPSCs will be used and stored under good laboratory practice conditions that ensure safe growth and manipulation, as defined in the EU Directive 2004/23/EC on setting standards of quality and safety for the donation, procurement, testing, processing preservation, storage and distribution of human tissues and cells. After the experimentation, the materials will be disposed according to pre- described and approved protocols and guidelines.

Animal experiments will be also performed, to compare the patterns of neural activity recorded in organoids to those obtained *in vivo*, with the goal of assessing the validity of the *in vitro* model to replace animal experiments. As regards national legal - and ethical requirements, UVA, which is the partner where animal experiments will be carried out, will make sure that all experimental procedures will adhere to the European and national legislation. UVA PI is a FELASA Category B certified researcher ("Article 9 person" under national regulations), which gives authorization to autonomously design and perform animal experiments. The UVA team has a significant experience in obtaining ethical approval

to perform animal experiments. Following national legislation (which complies with Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes), any experiment will require approval from a national Ethical Committee. This committee will evaluate all aspects related to animal husbandry, experimental procedures, number of animals and levels of suffering. Monitoring will be performed by the Animal Welfare Office of the Institution involved, as well as via internal inspections by faculty members. Any modification to the experimental protocol will need approval by the Animal Welfare Officer and/or by the Ethics Committee. Approval for the proposed experiments is currently being requested. The approved experimental protocol and the communication of acceptance from the Ethics committee will be communicated once they have been finalized.

As regards human sleep habits, data will be collected (or have already been collected) using actigraphy in conjunction with polysomnography scoring provided by the project's academic partners. These data will be anonymised at the source, ensuring that identifiable information (e.g., participants' names and surnames) is destroyed immediately after the data collection phase. Following anonymisation, only de-identified metadata about participants (e.g., age, sex, disease stage) will be retained. These metadata will serve as the only information shared among project partners, including Sleepacta, which will use this dataset to train the new neural network for sleep-wake prediction. This process will utilize movement data and polysomnography scoring in strict compliance with ethical standards and data protection regulations.

Participants will be required to provide informed consent before participation, and access to the anonymised data will be strictly limited to project investigators, authorized research staff, and members of the local ethics committee or review board, unless otherwise required by law.

It should be noted that since NAP is a collaborative project involving different countries and regulations, all project partners must adhere to specific provisions of the international and national regulations, as also stated in the Grant Agreement. The consortium will pay particular attention to ensure the compliance to all local, national and European regulations in matter of data protection and privacy, in particular the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Parliament and the Council of the EU (EU Regulation 2016/679 of 27 April 2016).

As regards the gender balance, inspired by the EC Policy review on Inclusive Analysis¹, NAP embraced the importance of taking an inclusive and participatory approach to address gender inequalities in all phases of the research project. This consideration will tackle the activities implemented during research and the outcomes of research. Indeed, it is imperative to be aware of the existence of biases (e.g., the digital divide in the access/use of the technologies between men and women) and true differences (e.g., the sex differences reported in literature for sleep diseases and neurodegenerative disorders). NAP research will try to reduce the effect of such biases and differences. As outlined in the Grant Agreement, the partners will incorporate sex analysis into research and innovation contents and management activities to ensure that the sex and gender dimensions are properly considered, removing potential barriers to adoption and take-up.

The sample size for each of the category included will be reported in the Data Management Plan (DMP, D1.2).

The ethics self-assessment is reported in Appendix 2.

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/knowledge-publications-tools-and-data/publications/all-publications/gendered-innovation-2-how-inclusive-analysis-contributes-research-and-innovation_en

Ethics management in NAP

Organizational bodies and ethics management

The project management structure of the project is part of the Consortium Agreement. The structure foresees a set of organizational bodies responsible for the execution, coordination, monitoring and supervision of the project activities:

- 1) The *General Assembly*, which is the highest decision body of the project, supervises and makes decisions on key issues related to the project. In the case of ethics issues, the General Assembly will be consulted;
- 2) The *Scientific Coordinator*, which supervises and coordinates all the scientific activities of the projects, including ethical issues;
- 3) The *Board of the Ethical Management*, which is an external consulting body composed of experts in ethics; they will be updated regularly on the work progress of the consortium to provide guide and opinions on specific issues. They may be also consulted in case ethics issues arise.
- 4) The *Legal and Ethical Board*, which is a consulting body of experts in legal and ethical aspects, may arise once the NAP Proof of Principle (i.e., the development of an innovative biohybrid enabling technology for long-term monitoring of sleep and wake states *in vitro*, as stated in the Description of Action, Grant Agreement) will be demonstrated.

In case an issue connected to any ethics principle will emerge during the execution of the activities, the involved actor identifying the issue will have to inform the organizational bodies to share the issue and agree on appropriate actions. The process of managing ethics issues in NAP follows a specific framework, involving three stages:

- 1) raising awareness on ethics requirements;
- 2) monitoring;
- 3) resolution of problems and/or identification of mitigation measures.

All the organizational bodies are informed about and aware of the ethics issues in NAP. They will participate in the ethics principles implementations. All partners have previous experience in participation in EU-funded projects and familiar with ethic issues highlighted in this document. In addition, the principles were also stated during the kick-off meeting by the members of the Board of the Ethical Management and the Legal and Ethical Board.

Practices for monitoring ethics management

Several practices have been and are being adopted for guaranteeing that all the people involved within the project are aware of the ethics issues, specifically for the early career researchers recruited. In particular:

- 1) Presentation during the kick-off meeting by the members of the boards, where the key ethics principles in research, the need to adhere to them and the recall of the ethics issues already identified in the Grant Agreement were recalled;
- 2) Presentation of the present deliverable. Its content was shared among the partners, to sensitize them to the need to comply with ethics principles. Since NAP is a 42 months-project, and it is likely that new researchers and non-scientific staff will be involved during its lifespan, this document will be also shared among them for letting them be aware about ethics issues;
- 3) E-meeting with the Board of the Ethical Management and the Legal and Ethical Board. The Scientific Coordinator will update the members of the board every three months about the

scientific and technological progresses, for teasing out any other ethics issues to be discussed and faced;

- 4) A document shared with the Scientific Coordinator and the members of the Boards, where they collect any issues, through the lifespan of the project and the ones may arise beyond NAP.
- 5) Dedicated sessions during the annual consortium meeting, to recall the key ethics requirements and for discussing any actions to be taken to raise awareness and prevent ethics issues.

Conclusions

This deliverable aims at offering guidelines for addressing ethics in the NAP project. The key principles that inspire ethical research and that must be monitored during the project implementation are related to the Grant Agreement, to the need of respecting human rights and the balance of benefits and harms, and to the management of data and privacy, the gender balance, and the informed consent of all participants.

Ethics management is addressed in NAP through the identification of organisational bodies who contribute in different forms to the identification, monitoring, and decision making and through the definition of an ethics management process. All researchers and non-scientific staff participating in the project will be properly informed and trained (as stated in the Section 'Practices for monitoring the ethics management') on ethics issues, and they will be responsible for identifying possible issues.

A set of resources (e.g., protocols for cell storing and maintenance) has been defined to address some specific issues that are peculiar to the project. All partners will comply with national and European legislation, in line with national data protection provisions and the European data protection rules (GDPR). The participants will also implement specific provisions when recording, analysing, and storing data, as will be highlighted in the Data Management Plan (D1.2).

In accordance with the HORIZON agenda, the gender balance will be addressed in the analysis of the research data, in order to avoid gender-related biases.

Appendix

Appendix 1 - Ethical dimension of the objectives, methodology and likely impact

Use of stem cells

We will use hiPSCs from PD patients and healthy volunteers for generating the cerebral organoids and then the hybrid constructs, i.e., the cyborganoids. UNIPi and UVA, which will handle the samples provided by OT for their own research activities, have direct access to appropriate labs and research centres and to technicians with long-standing expertise in performing experiments involving cells.

Animal experiments

The procedures for the animal experiments are all performed at UVA. The NAP project aims to develop a new *in vitro* experimental model for neuroscientific investigation, with the potential to greatly reduce the experimental activities which actually require to be performed *in vivo*. For this reason, we believe the use of laboratory animals is to be deemed acceptable, given the potential outcome of the project.

It is however of primary importance to minimize the number of employed animals and avoid any unnecessary painful experience. In particular, we will comply with the principles of the 3 Rs in animal research: reduction, refinement and replacement. The following specific points will be taken into account:

Choice of animal species: mice are the phylogenetically "lowest" animal species that can be employed for the UVA part of the project. Smaller laboratory animal (e.g., *Drosophila*) have brains that are too different from those of humans (from which the cells to develop the brain organoids will be harvested). The use of simpler animal models would thus greatly limit the obtainable results and, especially, the possibility to translate the results to humans. Indeed, many studies have revealed a homology between the organization of the neocortex in mice and that in higher mammals. The use of higher mammals (cats, ferrets, non-human primates) would pose limits to our experimental activities as: i) limited validated strategies exist for performing two-photon calcium imaging in higher mammals and ii) the presence of cortical convolutions would currently limit the possibility of properly access the cortical surface (as the mice cortex does not present any convolution). Importantly, despite the absence of cortical convolutions, mice have long been considered a prime model to study neuronal sleep dynamics (see e.g., 21-22, 40 48-49). In fact, the characteristics of neuronal activity patterns during sleep are preserved across mammals, independently on whether brains present circumvolutions or not. This pertains both the spatio-temporal properties of sleep slow oscillations, their travelling properties, as well as their circuit-level underpinnings. Thus, the use of mice as animal models is not foreseen to be a problem when comparing the results to those obtained in human *cyborganoids*.

Number of animals: We will take all measures necessary to minimize the number of animals to be employed. We expect a limited number of animals (less than 50) to be necessary to test the effectiveness of our technological developments. These numbers include the possibility of unsuccessful experiments as well as pilot experiments.

Pain minimization: the proposed project involves several phases in which animals could potentially suffer, i.e. surgery and recovery, sensory/behavioural experiments, euthanasia. At each stage, all necessary precautions will be taken to minimize animal suffering. We have a long-standing experience concerning all these stages. Surgeries will be performed under isoflurane anaesthesia (4% concentration for induction, 1.5% for maintenance), and local lidocaine injections will be performed on the scalp to minimize potential pain. Painkillers will be systemically administered during the post-surgery recovery phase. Animals will be implanted with a chronic head bar and cranial window for enabling to perform imaging. In our experience, animals tolerate this type of implant very well and

can recover in a day following surgery. Viral injections for the expression of calcium indicators and opsins have not been reported to induce long-lasting discomfort after surgery. The use of non-replicating (AAV) viruses ensures that the infection will not spread out of control. Euthanasia will normally be performed by an overdose of pentobarbital (intra-peritoneal injection).

Humane endpoint: animals' well-being will be constantly monitored to detect any sign of pain or distress. Initial interventions will be performed with systemic painkillers, followed by euthanasia if pain or distress cannot be alleviated. Experimental sessions will be interrupted in case of evident distress or pain, and animals will be allowed to rest and recover. In case of an arising pathology, euthanasia will be applied.

Humans

In NAP, humans will be recruited for tracking their own sleep habits using the signals acquired with wearables and analysed using the SleepActa Artificial Neural networks. As such, we will take care of the privacy protection and storage of personal data. Specifically, no information will be collected concerning sexual lifestyle, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction.

Regarding the PD patients, the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the recruitment have been identified by the partners and detailed in Table 2.

Table 2 Inclusion/Exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Age between 50 and 85 years old	Paediatric populations
A clinical diagnosis of Parkinson Disease	Not stable on dose of FDA-approved medications for Parkinsons' Disease
Participants not too impaired to perform the tests	Presence of another condition that may impact the result of the sleep analysis.

Regarding the healthy volunteers, we will recruit people without any diagnoses of sleep problems.

Appendix 2 – Ethics issue table of the NAP project

The last column refers to the page numbers in the Description of Action outlined in the Grant Agreement.

Human Embryonic Stem Cells and Human Embryos	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells?		X	
Does this activity involve Human Embryos?		X	
Humans	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve Human Participants?	X		5
Are they volunteers for non-medical studies (e.g., social or human sciences research)?		X	
Are they healthy volunteers for medical studies?	X		5-6
Are they patients for medical studies?		X	
Are they potentially vulnerable individuals or groups?		X	
Are they children/minors?		X	
Are they other persons unable to give informed consent?		X	
Does this activity involve interventions (physical also including imaging technology, behavioural treatments etc. on the study participants)?		X	
Does this activity involve conducting a clinical study as defined by the Clinical Trial Regulation (EU 536/2014)? (using pharmaceuticals, biologicals, radiopharmaceuticals, or advanced therapy medicinal products)		X	
Human cells/Tissues (not covered by Section1)	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve the use of human cells or tissues?	X		5-6
Are they human embryonic or foetal cells or tissues?		X	
Are they available commercially?		X	
Are they obtained from this project?	X		5
Are they obtained from another project, laboratory or institution?		X	
Are they obtained from biobanks?		X	
Personal Data	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve processing of personal data?		X	
Does this activity involve further processing of previously collected personal data (including use of preexisting data sets or sources, merging existing data sets)??	X		5
It is planned to export personal data from the EU to non-EU countries? Specify the type of personal data and countries involved		X	
It is planned to export personal data from non-EU countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country? Specify the type of personal data and countries involved		X	
Does this activity involve the processing of personal data related to criminal convictions or offences?		X	
Animals	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve animals?	X		5-6
Are they vertebrates?	X		5-6
Are they non-human primates?		X	
Are they genetically-modified?	X		5-6
Are they cloned farm animals?		X	
Are they endangered species?		X	
Non-EU countries	Yes	No	Page
Will some of the activities be carried out in non-EU countries?		X	
In case non-EU countries are involved, do the activities undertaken in these countries raise potential ethics issues?		X	

It is planned to use local resources (e.g. animal and/or human tissue samples, genetic material, live animals, human remains, materials of historical value, endangered fauna or flora samples, etc.)?		X	
Is it planned to import any material (other than data) from non-EU countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country?		X	
Is it planned to export any material (other than data) from the EU to non-EU countries?		X	
Does this activity involve low and/or lower middle-income countries, (if yes, detail the benefit -sharing actions planned in the self-assessment)		X	
Could the situation in the country put the individuals taking part in the activity at risk?		X	
Environment, Health and Safety	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve the use of substances or processes that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants (during the implementation of the activity or further to the use of the results, as a possible impact)?		X	
Does this activity deal with endangered fauna and/or flora / protected areas?		X	
Does this activity involve the use of substances or processes that may cause harm to humans, including those performing the activity (during the implementation of the activity or further to the use of the results, as a possible impact)		X	
Artificial Intelligence	Yes	No	Page
Does this activity involve the development, deployment and/or use of Artificial Intelligence? (if yes, detail in the self-assessment whether that could raise ethical concerns related to human rights and values and detail how this will be addressed).		X	
Other Ethics Issues	Yes	No	Page
Are there other ethics issues that should be taken into considerations?		X	

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON EIC programme under grant agreement No 101099310.